

NOTES

Studies on Complexes of Copper(II) with 3-Methyl-2,6-diphenylpiperidin-4-one and 3,5-Dimethyl-2,6-diphenylpiperidin-4-one

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LITERATURE survey reveals that no attempt has been made so far to synthesise and characterise the complexes of copper(II) with piperidin-4-ones. We report here the synthesis and characterisation of a few complexes of copper(II) with 3-methyl-2,6-diphenylpiperidin-4-one (L_1) and 3,5-dimethyl-2,6-diphenylpiperidin-4-one (L_2).

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The ligands were prepared by the reported method¹. The complexes were prepared by mixing hot ethanolic solutions of copper salts with hot ethanolic solutions of the ligands in 1 : 1 molar ratio with a slight excess of the ligand and refluxing the mixture for 1–4 h. In the case of CuSO_4 , DMF was used as the solvent. The resulting solid complexes were washed with hot ethanol and dried under reduced pressure.

Estimation of metal and anions were carried out by standard procedures². The ligands were estimated by decomposing the complexes by adding first glacial acetic acid and then dilute H_2SO_4 and estimating³ the piperidone released using KMnO_4 .

Magnetic susceptibility of the complexes at room temperature was measured by Gouy method using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_4]$ as the calibrant. Molar conductance of solutions (DMF) of the complexes was measured using a Toshniwal conductivity bridge. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 597 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra (MeOH) on a Jasco UVIVDEC-437 spectrophotometer. TG and DTA studies were carried out on a Shimadzu instrument with DT-40 thermal analyser.

Results and Discussion

The complexes (Table 1) are sparingly soluble in ethanol, acetone, ether and nitrobenzene, but soluble in DMF.

Analytical data of the complexes correspond to 1 : 1 metal : ligand stoichiometry. The molecular formulae of the complexes could be represented as $\text{CuL}_2\text{H}_2\text{O}\cdot\text{X}_2$ ($\text{X}=\text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{NO}_3, \text{ClO}_4$ and $1/2 \text{SO}_4$; $\text{L}=\text{L}_1, \text{L}_2$). Molar conductance of $\sim 10^{-3}M$ solutions of the complexes in DMF lie in the range $130-160 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ indicating 1 : 2 electrolytic nature. Electrolytic behaviour of the complexes in DMF, ethanol and acetone are further evident by the immediate precipitation of Cl^- and Br^- by the addition of alcoholic AgNO_3 .

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				μ_{eff}	Molar cond. $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$
		Cu	Ligand	Anion	H_2O		
$[\text{CuL}_1(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	Green	14.40 (14.60)	58.20 (60.80)	16.00 (16.30)	8.10 (8.30)	1.60	132.0
$[\text{CuL}_1(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Br}_2$	Bright green	12.08 (12.10)	49.80 (50.52)	29.80 (30.50)	6.40 (6.86)	1.64	166.8
$[\text{CuL}_1(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{SO}_4$	Bluish green	13.40 (13.80)	56.50 (57.54)	20.21 (20.84)	7.40 (7.80)	2.05	155.0
$[\text{CuL}_1(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2](\text{NO}_3)_2$	Blue	12.80 (13.00)	53.82 (54.24)	26.00 (25.38)	7.21 (7.36)	1.60	153.0
$[\text{CuL}_1(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$	Blue	10.90 (11.20)	46.50 (47.03)	34.40 (35.36)	6.60 (6.38)	1.75	159.4
$[\text{CuL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	Green	14.04 (14.10)	61.40 (62.07)	15.10 (15.79)	7.75 (8.00)	1.63	152.0
$[\text{CuL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Br}_2$	Bright green	12.00 (11.80)	50.98 (51.80)	28.92 (29.71)	6.45 (6.68)	1.73	158.0
$[\text{CuL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{SO}_4$	Blue	13.68 (13.38)	57.90 (58.79)	20.10 (20.31)	6.05 (6.28)	1.90	155.0
$[\text{CuL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2](\text{NO}_3)_2$	Blue	12.80 (12.64)	56.10 (55.51)	24.30 (24.67)	6.92 (7.16)	1.79	165.0
$[\text{CuL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$	Blue	11.16 (11.00)	47.86 (48.31)	33.80 (34.49)	6.50 (6.23)	1.63	132.0

* $\text{L}_1=3\text{-Methyl-2,6-diphenylpiperidin-4-one}$; $\text{L}_2=3,5\text{-dimethyl-2,6-diphenylpiperidin-4-one}$.

TG curve of $[\text{CuL}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ ($\text{L} = 3\text{-methyl-2,6-diphenylpiperidin-4-one}$) around 160° shows a weight-loss corresponding to the elimination of two molecules of water. An endothermic peak is also observed in the DTA curve around 160° , further confirming the elimination of water. An inflection is observed around 450° in the TG curve. An exothermic peak observed around the same temperature in the DTA curve may be attributed to the oxidative decomposition of the complex.

The observed room temperature magnetic moments (1.62–2.03 B.M.) indicate the presence of one unpaired electron.

Ir spectra of the ligands show a sharp band at 1690 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{O}$), which shifts to a higher frequency by $30\text{--}40\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in all the complexes⁴. This shows the involvement of CO group in bonding to the metal. The ligands show a sharp band at 3300 cm^{-1} (N-H). The presence of split bands with reduced intensity in the complexes in the range $3350\text{--}3150\text{ cm}^{-1}$ suggests splitting of N-H bands due to coordination through nitrogen⁵. The piperidones essentially behave as bidentate and chelating ligands. Further, it is believed⁶ that the free ligands are in chair form and the chelating structures proposed for the complexes demand boat conformation in the complexes.

The presence of vibrational bands around 3450 , 1640 and $920\text{--}650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes are characteristic of the presence of coordinated water⁷. Electronic spectra of the complexes show a broad band around 14300 cm^{-1} which can be assigned to the transition, ${}^3E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$, indicating square-planar geometry⁸. The high intensity band observed around 31000 cm^{-1} is attributed to $\text{L} \rightarrow \text{M}$ charge transfer transition⁶.

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